

Madurai Nayaka's Dilapidated Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple at Maravapatti Village of Vadipatti Taluk - Architectural Engineering a Field Report

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Abstract:- Temples are cultural houses that expose art and architecture. The strength of the temple is based on its maintenance, architectural material and environment. Constructing a temple; maintaining and preserving temple architecture is a very big task. Madurai Nayaks were Vaishnavites, but they extended their patronage to all the Hindu sects. They were busy with people's beliefs and constructed many Dravidian-style new temples in vital cities and rural villages. They extended many temple inner and outer prakaras, pillars mandapas; temple pounds. They repaired old temples and renovated Rajagopuras, Vimanas and boundary walls etc. Still date so many Madurai Nayak temples are rich in architectural beauty, sculptural beauty, and cultural transformation and it says about Madurai Nayak's religious contributions to devotees. At the same time, some old temples are located in rural villages of Madurai surroundings which were constructed by the Madurai Nayaks period. This paper deals with the Madurai Nayak period a dilapidated Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple which is situated in Madurai District, Vadipatti Taluk, at Maravapatti village on Natham Palamedu road. This paper is written about the said Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple plan, embossed sculpture, reason for dilapidation, damaged places and recommendation for repair and renovation of old temple. Regarding this dilapidated temple, the above-mentioned research authors report in the succeeding paragraph.

Keywords:- Madurai Nayak, Ground Plan, Embossed Sculpture, Vijayanagar Sculpture Narasimha, Fish Symbol, Palaiyakkarrars.

I. INTRODUCTION

Under the Vijayanagara emperor, the Madurai region around 131 years was ruled by nine nayaks by the name of Amaranayakas from 1404 C.E. to 1535 C.E.¹ Later, the formation of the Madurai Nayakdom was begun in 1529 C.E., under the Vijayanagar Empire Krishnadeva Raya. Viswanatha Nayak was the first Nayak ruler of Madurai Nayakdom and the dynasty ruled up to 1736 C.E. Around 207 year's history of Madurai Nayadom a total of 13 rulers ruled the kingdom proudly. In the beginning, Viswanatha

Nayaka introduced a new system in the Madurai Kingdom with the advice of his Dalavay Ariyanatha Mudhaliyar, he divided his region into 72 bastions which were called Palayams.² It was lead by Palaiyakkarrars (Poligars), he maintain an army and render help to the Nayaks.³ The Madurai Nayak ruler spends enormous money for constructed of new temples, manapas, road edifice, ponds, cannels, renovation of old temples, extension of temples and old manapas and took care under direct control of the temple administration.⁴ Madurai Nayak's and his subordinate constructed many Dravidian style temples and they very strictly followed the geometrical construction called vastu-purusha-mandala for the design and construction of the ground floor plan. It consists of Rajagopuram, Muga mandapa, Maha mandapas, Artha Mandpas, Garbhagiraha (sanctum sanatorium) gopuras, pillar halls, Vasantha mandaps etc. and architectural structures using granite stones. In some places, they used burned bricks for the construction of Rajagopuram and sanctum sanatorium gopuram.⁵ At presently, these temples always say their names. In many temples, much number of authentic inscriptions are inscribed and say about Madurai Nayak's and their subordinate officer's name and their contributions. But at the same time in some temples, inscriptions were not inscribed, but they belonged to Madurai Nayaks period temples or their subordinate officers constructed temples. A similar temple is identified by the authors of the paper in Madurai's rural area i.e. Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple at Maravapatti village in Madurai District in Tamilnadu.

➤ Location of the Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple

Madurai Nayak period Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple is situated in 'Madurai District, Vadipatti Taluk, Alankanallur Panchayat Union, at Rajakkalpatti village, Maravapatti'⁶ Panchayat on Natham Palamedu Road towards East. This old temple site is located at 10.1267997^o Latitude and 78.1124319^o Longitude surrounded by fully cultivation land near the KGP Gardens and Sri Atheya Avadhootha Ashram which is around 2 km near Rajakkalpatti and Maravapatti Villages and around 34 km from Madurai Junction Railway Station in Tamilnadu. This temple is called as Old Perumal Temple or Old Vishnu Temple⁷ shown Map. Picture 1.

Picture 1 Madurai Junction to Old Permal Temple Site.

➤ *Ground Plan of the Entire Temple*

The entire Sri Varadaraja Perumal temples outside boundary walls are constructed of burned brick. Inside the temple, there are two stone temples are constructed and its structures are seen in heavily damaged condition. Inside the temple complex, the left side temple is considered the Perumal temple and the right side temple is considered to be the Mahalakshmi (Amman) temple. During the ‘Vijayanagar period, Amman shrines were built on the south-western corners. ⁸ In this temple Mahalakshmi (Amman) temple is located at south west corner.

Picture 2 Block Diagram Ground Plan of the Temple

Both the temples are made of granite stones. This temple's complete walls in Garbhagraha, Artha Mandapam and Maha Mandapam were constructed with a double-stone wall structure around 2.3 feet wide. The insides of the temple chamber wall and outside of the temple wall stone are nicely polished. In between these double stone walls have been filled with a mixture of broken burned bricks with lime powder and river sand. Its upper part is found in a dilapidated condition. Also, Vimana is seen in both temples and it was constructed with burned bricks. Many pillars have sculptures in good condition. Each temple has a stone slab roof that is seen in damaged condition. This temple is not maintained. The entire temple ground plan is given as per Block Diagram.2. The total area of the Sri Varadaraja

Perumal temple complex is 23,600 square feet (0.54 Acres), whereas the length is 200 feet and the breadth is 118 feet. Inside the temple complex, Mahalakshmi Amman temple alone is around 1000 square feet area and Perumal temple alone is around 1455 square feet area. In between the two temples, around 20 feet distance. Each temple structure is divided into four sections. It is consisting of Garbhagraha, Arthamandapam, Maha Mandapam, and Muga Mandapam. This temple faces eastern directions and the main entrance of the temple was in heavily damaged condition.

➤ *Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple View this Temple Shown As Per Picture.3.*

Picture 3 Entire Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple

➤ *Muga Mandapam*

The Perumal temple structure is divided into four sections. It is consisting of Garbhagraha, Arthamandapam, Maha Mandapam, and Muga Mandapam. In the Muga Mandapam (front mandapam) a six-pillar open hall is found to be grafted pillars.

<p>Karuppasamy</p>	<p>Lord Vishnu (Kaliyakrishna)</p>	<p>A half Moon and Full Sun symbol</p>
<p>Hanuman</p>	<p>Eagle opened the beak and Elephant</p>	
<p>Purana Kumbam</p>	<p>Lingam</p>	<p>Yali</p>

Picture 4 Stone Sculpture Muga Mandapa Pillar Embossed sculpture

The length at the outside edge to edge of the mandapam is 26 feet length and the width is 14 feet. Stairs led from three sides to enter the three sides open front hall. There are four pillars in the front row and one pillar each in the side row. 'A Half Moon and Full Sun symbol' embossed sculpture is seen on the top of the Eastern side of the 2nd pillar and 1st pillar northern side bottom. The Madurai Nayak rulers issued coins with the half-moon and sun symbol as royal emblem.⁹ Also, they inscribed many inscription sun symbols as royal emblem. So, this embossed sculpture also seen this temple. hence it strong evidence it is belongs to Madurai Nayak constructed temple. The eastern and northern sides of the 4th pillar are engraved embossed sculptures of Siva lingam. Stone pillar embossed sculpture of the Perumal temple muga mandapa are shown as per picture.4. Eastern side of the 6th pillar a Hanuman embossed sculpture, Western side of the same pillar on the top an Eagle opened the beak and an Elephant, Lord Vishnu and Karuppasamy embossed sculpture engraved. A Fish symbol is seen in-between linking the 1st & 2nd Pillar beams; dual fish symbol opposing each other is seen in-between linking the 2nd & 3rd Pillar beams; 3rd & 4th Pillar beams and 4th & 5th Pillar beams. Also, a big corbel seen on 1st 3rd, 4th and 6th pillars of Muga Mandapam. Each pillar is 10.1 feet in height and 6.5 feet in width. Perumal temple mugamandapa pillars embossed sculpture shown as per Stone Sculpture.3. There are many sculptures found in Joint Pillar or Ottuthun. While going up the stairs to enter the temple from the southern side, a very finely carved sculpture can be seen on the east-facing pillar. There is a sculpture of a man who can be seen holding a sword and full body adorned with ornaments that look like Karuppasamy. Beside it, a lion makes a majestic appearance. The sculpture at the top of the pillar shows standing on an animal with both feet and holding the animal's tail with a hand. Above that, the sculpture at the beginning of the pillar is of an elephant. A sculpture that looks like an elephant's face and a lion's face looking at each other is found in this pillar. The pillar consists of a

rectangle, square, number bar, square, number bar, and square from bottom to top. These sculptures are found on the western side of the pillar. No sculpture is found on the south side of the pillar. A flower-shaped structure is seen only in the lower part.

➤ *Gajalakshmi Embossed Sculpture:*

On entering the Maha mandapam of the Perumal temple, an embossed sculpture of Gajalakshmi is seen above the entrance door. She is depicted holding a lotus in her left hand and the lotus cornice in her right hand and there are two elephants blessing posture on both sides. On the right and left sides of the Maha mandapam embossed Vishnu Sudarshana Chakra on the right side and a conch on the left side. Also, above the Gajalakshmi embossed sculpture, a beautiful flying angle (Devathai) image is engraved. Gajalakshmi Embossed sculpture shown as per Picture.5. Mukha Mandapam of the Mahalakshmi Amman Temple is located on the right side of the temple complex. In front of the staircase, on each side, there are two welcoming humanoid statues. The staircase, which may be facing east, consists of five steps. A small Yazhi structure is seen flanking the steps leading up to the Muga mandapam from the south. The Muga mandapam roof over the temple is damaged condition due to heavy stone weight and non-maintenance of the temple. The roof stones have six pairs of fish symbols engraved. In the Muga Mandapam, a six-pillar open hall is found to be grafted pillars. On the top of the eastern side, four pillars are engraved embossed sculptures of Vijayanagar sculpture of Narasimha and on the bottom of the pillar, a man in Anjali posture embossed sculpture facing western direction. On the bottom of the 3rd pillar, two Anjali posture embossed sculptures engraved facing west and northern directions. The length at the outside edge to edge of the mandapam is 21.2 feet length and the width is 13.9 feet. Stairs led from two sides to enter the three sides open front hall.

Picture 5 Gajalakshmi, Vishnu Sudarshana Chakra, Conch and a Beautiful Flying Angle (Devathai) Embossed Sculpture

There are four pillars in the front row and one each pillar in the side row. Sculptures carved on the pillars, especially the lotus, snake, lion vehicle, human figures, fish symbols, bird figures, otuthutun (joint pillar) etc are found in the Muga Mandapam pillars. Upon entering the temple, the slab stone above between two pillars in the front hall has two opposing fish symbols are identified. This fish symbol is emblem of Palaiyakkarars (Poligarsygars) of Madurai Nayaks. Extension of the Muga Mandapam has a 6 x 3.30 feet entrance door connection the Maha Mandapam. Above the entrance leading from the front Mandapam to the Maha Mandapam, a stone Gajalakshmi goddess embossed sculpture found between two elephants.

➤ *Stone Sculpture in Muga Mandapam Entrance:*

In front of the Amman temple Maha Mandapa, a half-buried two standing posture stone pillar sculptures are carved. Two men standing posture sculpture looking at each other with the Anjali mudra is visually related to the Namaste gesture shown as per stone sculpture.6. This

posture denotes devotion, welcoming all the devotees with respect and in another sense, it gives more respect to the deity. It is believed that men's stone sculptures located on the right side of the Amman temple may be a Madurai Nayak because on the eastern side of the pillar embossed half moon and sun symbols. On the bottom of the same stone is a man's sculpture in small size. He may be Nayak's son or brother. The left side of the Amman temple muga mandapa is located another stone sculpture, it may be the local Palaiyakkarars of Madurai Nayakdom.

But the names of the Madurai Nayaks and local Palaiyakkarars have not been mentioned in any place of the temple premises. It is also believed that in the Hindu religion, if nameless donations done by any devotee for temple construction, repair and renovation and donations are if done will be given moksha after devotees' mukti. So, the ruler may have followed the method and so it is believed that he did not inscribed inscription in temple premises.

Picture 6 Mukha Mandapam Entrance

➤ *Maha Mandapam*

In Perumal temple, the extension of the Muga Mandapam is connected to the Maha Mandapam. Inside the chamber, along the wall of the Maha Mandapam, four pillars are found. It is seen that from the end of the section between the Artha Mandapam and the Maha Mandapam in a straight line towards the east. The structure supporting the Pothikai, which is set up to, support the roof of the Maha Mandapam, and the pillar supporting structure is seen.

➤ *Maha Mandapa Pillar Embossed Sculptures*

Lion	Linga Yoni structure	Devotee hold a Dagger
Peacock	Deer	
Devotee Sculpture 1	Devotee Sculpture 2	
	Vijayanagar sculpture of Narasimha	
Devotee Sculpture 3	Kurma Sculpture Tortoise	

Picture 7 Maha Mandapa Pillar Embossed Sculptures in Perumal Temple

Slightly away from the wall. The length at the outside edge-to-edge measurement of the Maha mandapam length is 27 feet and the width is 26 feet. In this mandapa for air circulation and outside sunlight entering into the temple, a square-shaped hole pattern has been constructed. With the assistance of this hallowed structure, air circulation and sunlight will be entered inside the temple. On the two pillars on the right side of the Perumal temple Maha Mandapam embossed sculpture images of Yoga Narasimha, Conch, Vishnave Namah, Peacock, Tortoise and a woman. On the inner pillar on the left side of the Maha Mandapam, there are Chakras, Shiva, women etc emblazoned show as per Stone Sculpture.7.

- *Deer Sculpture:*

A pillar shows a sculpture of a scene set up where a deer eating food in a forest.

- *Kurma Sculpture:*

Tortoise is also known as Kurma. Kurma is listed as the second of the Dashavatara, which are the ten principal incarnations of Vishnu. This sculpture is seen on a pillar of the temple.

- *Devotee Holds a Dagger Sculpture:*

This stone pillar shows a sculpture of a devotee holding a shield in his left hand and a dagger in his right hand. The best view is to bring the left arm above the head and end with the knife and hold the shield in the right hand in front of the chest.

- *Devotee Sculptures 1, 2 and Peacock Sculptures:*

It beautifully depicts the Tamil culture of welcoming those who come to the temple with a Namaste posture. This sculpture is found buried in the soil. Only half of the sculpture is visible. A part of the pillar is broken. A Peacock holding a Scorpion tail in its mouth is depicted. The claws or Pedipalps of the Scorpion turned upward.

Picture 8 Joint Pillar Structure

- *Joint Pillar Structure:*

There are four pillars in the Maha Mandapam in the Amman Temple are found to be joint pillars. Inside wall of the right side Maha mandapam pillar, a half-hidden fish symbol is engraved. Inside of the Amma temple joint pillar and wall are white washed it shown as per picture.8. It is surprising to see that the pillars in the Perumal temple are ordinary. Vari Pothikai and Cut Pothikai also seen in Perumal temple mahamandapa. All the pillars in Maha Mandapam and Muga Mandapam are found in the small buds of the corbel decoration. Also, the pillar is carved small and the structure where the corbel can be found is large.

- *Artha Mandapam :*

Extension of the Maha Mandapam connected to the Artha Mandapam. Artha Mandapam is a small chamber. But it has no door. There is no sculpture and other beauties' engraved in this small chamber.

- *Garbhagraha :*

This Garbhagraha is completely built of stone. Measurement of the outside edge to edge of the Garbhagraha is 16x16 feet. In this square shape Garbhagraha, inside is missing the prime deity. The square-shaped Garbhagraha roof has been converted into an eight (diamond-shaped) corner roof by using slab stones and wooden beams. Between the timbers, bricks are tightly laid with lime mortar. Due to the non-maintenance of the temple, now, Garbhagraha is a living hut of bats and badly damaged condition. A fish symbol is engraved on the western side basement of the outer wall stone of the Perumal temple Garbhagraha. Also, a parrot and lion symbol is engraved on the Southern side basement outer wall stone of the Perumal temple Garbhagraha. This sculpture indirectly says, that inside of the Garbhagraha male and female deities are there. The sculpture is shown in Picture 9.

<p>Square shape Garbhagraha roof converted into a diamond-shaped roof</p>	<p>A fish symbol engraved at the western side basement of outer wall. In the fish head has observed elephant tusk.</p>	<p>Parrot and Lion embossed sculpture engraved</p>
	<p>Missing Statues in Garbhagraha: Inside the Garbhagraha, the sanctum sanctorum of Perumal Temple's original stone deities' statue is missing. But two statue stone basements measuring one and a half feet cuboid basements are present. According to the basement structures the statue may be at least three feet high. No inscription is seen inside the sanctum sanctorum. Inside the Garbhagraha of Mahalakshmi Amman Temple the original deities' are also missing.</p>	

Picture 9 Garbhagraha Sculpture

➤ *Vimana:*

Vimana is a vital part of the temple. The above-mentioned Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple complex the sanctum sanctorum of Perumal Temple and Mahalakshmi Amman was constructed by using the South Indian Dravidian Vimana structure. The sanctum sanctorum of Perumal temple was constructed using burned bricks. In the temple, the vimana simple elements Stupi (Final), Shikhara (Tower), Kudu, Griva (Neck), Tala Vahana, Shaala, Koota, Haara, Vyalaavari, Panjara, Pada, Adhithana are seen. But the stupi or kalasa is missing. Probably it may be fallout due to un-maintenance. This Vimana structure was plastered

with softy river sand and limestone paste. Now this Vimana is visible in black colour, plants are grown and a portion is partially damaged condition. Inside the temple complex, Perumal Temple Vimana's structure is a little big compared to Mahalakshmi Amman Temple Vimana. Also, this Vimana architecture can be seen with rich beautification. But this Vimana is also in damaged condition. An individual from a local village has tried to repair and renovate the Perumal Temple Vimana. So, its four sides are covered with coconut-slatted leaves. But work is stopped for an unknown reason. Both Vimana Structures are shown as per Picture.10.

<p>Mahalakshmi Amman Temple Vimana</p>	<p>Perumal Temple Vimana (covered with coconut-slatted leaves)</p>

Picture 10 Vimana of Perumal Temple

➤ *The Main Entrance Gate:*

The Varadaraja Perumal Temple is located opposite the hill's natural environment, now it is in ruin conditions. The entire temple fort wall was constructed with burned bricks and without a plastered. The main entranceway of the temple is in a ruined condition. It is damaged due to unwanted plants growth and its roots cracked out the wall. The main entranceway of the temple is at least 15 feet in

height, 20 feet in Length and 8 feet broad. Its wooden structure doors are open on the right and left sides the structure is also visible at the entrance gate. But it has fallen.

- Collapsed Portions of the Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple: Shown As Per Picture.11.

<p>Earlier View of Entrance Gate in 2020</p>	<p>Collapsed of Entrance Gate in 2022</p>
	<p>Damaged roof of the Mahalakshmi Amman temple: The roof of the Amman temple Muga mandapa is completely damaged condition. The roof is made of flat slab stones. The stones of the roof were shifting and falling and its partially broken slab stones were now in hanging. As it is left unmaintained, no one knows when it will collapse. So, it is very difficult for researchers for research work. Looking at the condition of this temple, if the community supporters come forward, there may be some way to fix the condition of this temple. It would be great if the government took this up.</p>
	<p>Amman Temple left side Maha mandapa damaged stone wall: In the temple walls of the Varadaraja Perumal Temple campus have Mahalakshmi Amman and Perumal temple which are constructed in three layers. Both deities' temples inside and outside stone walls are constructed with smoothly polished stones. In between the stone walls filling from limestone and brick mixtures. Both deities temple Maha Mandapam outer side walls both side are very badly dilapidated conditions. Stones can be seen falling out and plants can be seen sprouting from the limestone and brick of the middle wall.</p>
	<p>The right side outer stone wall of the Maha mandapa of the Permal Temple is in damaged condition.</p>
	<p>The left side of the outer stone wall of the Maha mandapa of the Perumal Temple is in damaged condition and also plants are grown.</p>
	<p>Open Well: A Stone well is found inside the temple complex between the Amman and Perumal temples. It is an outside edge-to-edge around 8x8 feet square-shaped well. The well, found to be floor to floor, is covered by trees and plants, so the depth cannot be calculated properly. With no manned environment to cap it or maintain it. The open well becomes very dangerous for visitors' (researchers) and cattles lives if not alerted.</p>

Picture 11 Collapsed Portions of the Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple

II. RESEARCH FINDINGS

Inside the temple, there is no inscription found out. However, it is identified that on a pillar of the muga and two pillars in maha mandapa of the temple, three Vijayanagar sculpture of Narasimha stone embossed sculpture. Madurai Nayak's emblems Half Moon with Sun sculpture and dual fish (facing at each other) embossed sculpture is identified inside of the Muga Mandapam on the right-side upper stone beam also identified. Outside of the temple, another dual fish half-broken embossed sculpture on a stone beam was traced by the authors. Also, Madurai Nayak's military general Palaiyakkarar's single fish embossed sculpture is identified at the sanctum sanctorum of the left outside side wall basement; right side Muga Mandapam of the Amman temple and right side wall of the maha mandapa of the temple. According to Vijayanagar sculpture Narasimha stone embossed figure, Madurai Nayak's emblem dual fish and Palaiyakkarar's single fish embossed sculptures evidence, it is estimated that the temple was constructed

around 400 to 450 years ago. Outside of the boundary wall of the temple, a commemoration hero stone lies on the ground. Measuring 2.5 x 1.5 feet stone, the upper part is conical in shape. 'It shows a well-dressed female in a standing posture beside the head with a child on her hip, holding a jar in her left hand. A male figure engraved a bow in her left hand and his right hand having touched a very well arrow and aiming posture'.¹⁰ This commemoration hero stone was shifted to the temple. An individual from local villages is involved cleaning, removing the plants on temple walls, leveling damaged portion of the temple premises and renovate repairing one Vimana is in progress by his own expense. Vijayanagar sculpture of Narasimha stone embossed sculpture; Madurai Nayak's emblem Half Moon with Sun sculpture & dual fish; Palaiyakkarar's single fish embossed sculptures; a commemoration hero stone and Fish with Crocodile Head; Fish Body with Elephant Face; and Elephant Face Fish are identified which is shown as per Picture.12.

<p>Vijayanagar sculpture of Narasimha & Madurai Nayak emblem sculpture.</p>	<p>Dual fish half-broken embossed sculpture and Palaiyakkarar's single fish embossed sculptures</p>	<p>Commemoration Hero Stone</p>
<p>Fish with Crocodile Head: Two fish bodies are inscribed fish body with the Crocodile heads. Both heads are opposite. Crocodile's teeth are very sharpie.</p>		
<p>Fish Body with Elephant Face: An image of the body of a fish and the head of an elephant is embedded in a sculpture on the outer (eastern side) wall of the Maha Mandapam of Mahalakshmi Amman temple. In the fish operculum (gill cover) near the head and caudal fin of the tail are present. The dorsal fin, adipose fin, anal fin, and pelvic fins (paired), are absent. The head portion of the fish is an elephant head with a trunk. The image of this fish engraved on the eaves all onlookers in awe.</p>		

Elephant Face Fish: On a stone slab on the roof of the Perumal temple muga mandapa Elephant face fish sculpture is engraved.

This fish has the trunk, tusk,

mouth, lips, eye, and head of elephant seen in the fish body. In the Opposite of the Elephant face fish, another ordinary fish is also engraved.

Picture 12 Vijayanagar Empire, Madurai Nayak's and Palaiyakkarar's Emblem

➤ *Reason for the Dilapidations:*

Dilapidated Varadaraja Perumal Temple is located in a remote site from Rajakkalpatti and Maravapatti villages. The temple is located on the cultivation field with semi-block and red soil. Wetness is not dried in the cultivation ground around the temple. At the same time, heavy stone slabs have been mounted on the Artha Mandapam, Maha Mandapam, and Muga Mandapam of the temple. Due to ground wetness and an overload of stone slab weights on the temple Maha Mandapam right and left side walls basement have sat down on the soil and fallen. The stone slabs are placed above the Artha Mandapam, Maha Mandapam, and Muga Mandapam. Above the stone slabs, seven lines on the middle and five lines on the left and right side (slope) used with burned bricks stage were constructed with a mixing of lime sand paste for rainwater drainage. Here, during the rainy season, the damaged lime sand structure sucked the water particles and did not dry properly. So, trees and unwanted vegetation have grown in rainy seasons. So, its deep roots have badly damaged the structure of the upper floors of the temple.

Above the sanctum sanctorum burned bricks Vimana structure has been constructed and it was plastered with assistance limes sand mixture paste. In the structure, the Peepal tree grows and its roots have damaged the Vimana structure. The temple general maintenance was inadequately maintained by the temple administration. Inside the temple, missing out on the gods and goddesses stone statues. The temple is in damaged condition but its prime gods and goddesses statues have shifted to some places near the village surroundings or hiding out in place within the temple premises. Regarding this, any correct information is not traced out either by local devotees/temple management or by historical research scholars. So with the help of high-pitch penetrating radar either by the district administration or state government Archaeological department should research/trace out the temple premises. It may be possible to find out some more information about the prime god statue of the temple. The entire Sri Varadaraja Perumal temples outside boundary wall are may be later constructed and it was not plastered so due to seasonally rainy damaged the walls.

➤ *Recommendation for Renovation of Reengineering*

Dilapidated Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple should take over direct control either by the state government Archaeological Department or the Hindu Religious and Charitable Endowments Department of Tamilnadu for repair and renovation with consultation of Heritage Conservation Committee and Structural Stability Committee. The original rundown Varadaraja Perumal temple structure should be dismantled with the assistance of a high-quality conservation and preservation architectural engineering team as per archaeological principles. All broken pillars, stone slabs and floor stones should be replaced. The re-engineering process will help empower the civil engineering/Archaeological students' research attitude and skill development. Needed adequate monetary power for repair, renovation and reengineering of the temple structure recovery of its original shape. So, the creation of awareness programs through media, exhibitions, seminars, conferences and symposiums from educational institutions down to the local village level. It is recommended that to the State and Union Governments of India, every educational institution should find at least one old monument around the place and adapt it for conservation as a best practice of the institution. A local Zamindar family had earlier managed this temple. There is a detailed enquiry needed for more information about the temple land, and stone metal deities of the temple.

III. CONCLUSION

Later Pandyas used twin fish with an in-middle sendu as the royal emblem. As a continuation, 'Madurai's first Nayak ruler Viswanatha Nayak issued many copper coins that showed the twin parallel fishes symbol¹¹ under Vijayanagar ruler. By continuation, many Palaiyakkarars under Madurai Nayaks used fishes as their royal symbol. Palaiyakkarars have mostly used fish with moustaches commonly used. It was visible in Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple premises also; the Madurai Nayak rulers issued coins with the half-moon and sun symbol as the royal emblem. So this temple belongs to the Madurai Nayak period. Nayaks were Vaishnavites, but they extended their patronage to all the Hindu sects. Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple was constructed with the high aim to encourage Vaishnavites of Hindu sects. From the entrance gate to the insides temple portions are in dilapidated condition. Boundary wall are un-plastered condition. Inside the premises of the temple, Mahalakshmi

Amman temple muga mandapa roof is in damaged condition. Outside of the right and left side maha mandapa walls and Dravidian style Vimana of Perumal temple and Amman temple are in damaged condition. Inside of the temple, missing out the gods and goddesses' images. Rituals and religious festivals are not conducted in the present condition either by local villagers or the government. Inside of the temple an innovative embossed sculptures of Fish with Crocodile heads, Fish bodies with Elephant trunks, and Elephant Face Fish with trunks and tusks are seen at temple pillars. Also, Vijayanagar sculpture Narasimha and Madurai Nayak Half Moon with Sun sculpture are seen in Muga mandapas and Maha mandas are in good condition. Inside the temple complex not is any encroachment. Outside of the temple boundary wall, approximately half acres of land are seen it is also expected that it belongs to temple land. The temple-damaged stones and sand materials are dumps are seen outside the temple wall. There is an urgent need for proper repair, renovation of reengineering of the Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple. Also, there is a need for initiation by either government or non-government organisations or local head support to maintain and administration of the temple's daily poojas, rituals and conduct the annual festivals of the Sri Varadaraja Perumal Temple.

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